

Supplementary material

Identification of Small RNAs in *Streptomyces clavuligerus* using High-Resolution Transcriptomics and Expression Profiling during Clavulanic Acid Production.

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Supplementary Figure S1. Boxplot showing the percentage of reads aligned to the genome of *S. clavuligerus* ATCC 27064 from multiple RNA-seq samples, both downloaded from the SRA database and generated in this study.

Supplementary Figure S2. Operon structure of the clavulanic acid biosynthetic gene cluster as determined from RNA-seq data using Rockhopper. Genes are represented by thick horizontal arrows. Transcriptional units (TUs) are depicted as groups of genes bound together by a light blue arrow. Green: transcriptional regulator; pale red: biosynthetic genes; grey: other genes; blue: transport-related genes; vertical green line: DasR binding site, a repressor dependent on N-acetylglucosamine.

Supplementary Figure S3. Number of predicted sRNAs by Rockhopper and APERO.

Supplementary Figure S4. Clavulanic acid production in soy protein isolate (ISP) medium.

Supplementary Figure S5. RNA-mRNA interactions predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 for the differentially expressed (DE) sRNAs at 96 hours. This interaction network shows down-regulated sRNAs. Blue circles represent mRNA genes. Yellow circles indicate sRNAs from *S. clavuligerus* annotated in RFAM (if annotated); green circles indicate sRNAs annotated in other organisms, and red circles indicate unknown sRNAs. Thicker edges represent stronger interactions. Networks were generated using Cytoscape.

Supplementary Figure S6. RNA-mRNA interactions predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 for the differentially expressed (DE) sRNAs at 72 hours. This interaction network shows upregulated sRNAs. Blue circles represent mRNA genes. Yellow circles indicate sRNAs from *S. clavuligerus* annotated in RFAM (if annotated); green circles indicate sRNAs annotated in other organisms, and red circles indicate unknown sRNAs. Thicker edges represent stronger interactions. Networks were generated using Cytoscape.

Supplementary Figure S7. RNA-mRNA interactions predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 for the differentially expressed (DE) sRNAs at 72 hours. This interaction network shows down-regulated sRNAs. Blue circles represent mRNA genes. Yellow circles indicate sRNAs from *S. clavuligerus* annotated in RFAM (if annotated); green circles indicate sRNAs annotated in other organisms, and red circles indicate unknown sRNAs. Thicker edges represent stronger interactions. Networks were generated using Cytoscape.

Supplementary Figure S8. RNA-mRNA interactions predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 for the differentially expressed (DE) sRNAs at 48 hours. This interaction network shows upregulated sRNAs. Blue circles represent mRNA genes. Yellow circles indicate sRNAs from *S. clavuligerus* annotated in RFAM (if annotated); green circles indicate sRNAs annotated in other organisms, and red circles indicate unknown sRNAs. Thicker edges represent stronger interactions. Networks were generated using Cytoscape.

Supplementary Figure S9. RNA-mRNA interactions predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 for the differentially expressed (DE) sRNAs at 48 hours. This interaction network shows down-regulated sRNAs. Blue circles represent mRNA genes. Yellow circles indicate sRNAs from *S. clavuligerus* annotated in RFAM (if annotated); green circles indicate sRNAs annotated in other organisms, and red circles indicate unknown sRNAs. Thicker edges represent stronger interactions. Networks were generated using Cytoscape.

J	Translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis	U	Intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport
A	RNA processing and modification	O	Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones
K	Transcription	X	Mobilome: prophages, transposons
L	Replication, recombination and repair	C	Energy production and conversion
B	Chromatin structure and dynamics	G	Carbohydrate transport and metabolism
D	Cell cycle control, cell division, chromosome partitioning	E	Amino acid transport and metabolism
Y	Nuclear structure	F	Nucleotide transport and metabolism
V	Defense mechanisms	H	Coenzyme transport and metabolism
T	Signal transduction mechanisms	I	Lipid transport and metabolism
M	Cell wall/membrane/envelope biogenesis	P	Inorganic ion transport and metabolism
N	Cell motility	Q	Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport and catabolism
Z	Cytoskeleton	R	General function prediction only
W	Extracellular structures	S	Function unknown

Supplementary Figure S10. Cluster of Orthologous Groups (COG) functional classification for gene products from mRNAs potentially interacting with the differentially expressed (DE) sRNAs at 72 hours.

J	Translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis	U	Intracellular trafficking, secretion, and vesicular transport
A	RNA processing and modification	O	Posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones
K	Transcription	X	Mobilome: prophages, transposons
L	Replication, recombination and repair	C	Energy production and conversion
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M	Cell wall/membrane/envelope biogenesis	P	Inorganic ion transport and metabolism
N	Cell motility	Q	Secondary metabolites biosynthesis, transport and catabolism
Z	Cytoskeleton	R	General function prediction only
W	Extracellular structures	S	Function unknown

Supplementary Figure S11. Cluster of Orthologous Groups (COG) functional classification for gene products from mRNAs potentially interacting with the differentially expressed (DE) sRNAs at 48 hours.

Supplementary Figure S12. Pathway reconstruction for gene products of mRNAs potentially interacting with the up-regulated (green) and down-regulated (red) sRNAs at 72 hours. Blue: Interacting mRNAs shared.

Supplementary Figure S13. Pathway reconstruction for gene products of mRNAs potentially interacting with the up-regulated (green) and down-regulated (red) sRNAs at 48 hours. Blue: Interacting mRNAs shared.

Supplementary Figure S14. Pathway reconstruction for *S. clavuligerus*, as a reference to compare with the Figure 11 and Supplementary Figure S12-S13.

Supplementary Figure S15. Cumulative distribution of the fraction of transcripts expressed in a given number of RNA-seq samples (left); and frequency of transcripts expressed (right), determined by TPM, in each number of RNA-seq samples for all annotated genes belonging to a BGC.

Supplementary Figure S16. Average number of samples in which the different regions harboring BGCs are expressed. WT: Wild-type strains. Description of each region is presented in Supplementary Table S3

Supplementary Figure S17. Secondary structure of "p_RNA_R_6021554-6021232. The structure was constructed by RNArtist.

Available online: <https://github.com/fjossinet/RNArtist>

Supplementary Table S1. NCBI accession numbers for genome assemblies used in the IGR comparison

Strain	Accession Number
<i>Streptomyces globosus</i> soil	GCF_003325375.1_ASM332537v1
<i>Streptomyces lavendulae</i> lavendulae CCM 3239	GCF_002803845.1_ASM280384v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. Mg1	GCF_000412265.2_ASM41226v2
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. fd1-xmd	GCF_002007685.1_ASM200768v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. TN58	GCF_001941845.1_ASM194184v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. Sge12	GCF_002080455.1_ASM208045v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. 3211	GCF_002028385.1_ASM202838v1
<i>Streptomyces spongiicola</i> HNM0071	GCF_003122365.1_ASM312236v1
<i>Streptomyces tirandamycinicus</i> HNM0039	GCF_003097515.1_ASM309751v1
<i>Streptomyces rubrolavendulae</i> MJM4426	GCF_001750785.1_ASM175078v1
<i>Streptomyces exfoliatus</i> A1013Y	GCF_005517195.1_ASM551719v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. WAC00288	GCF_002943895.1_ASM294389v1
<i>Streptomyces venezuelae</i> NRRL B-65442	GCF_001886595.1_ASM188659v1
<i>Streptomyces vietnamensis</i> GIMV4.0001	GCF_000830005.1_ASM83000v1
<i>Streptomyces lunaelactis</i> MM109	GCF_003054555.1_ASM305455v1
<i>Streptomyces pristinaespiralis</i> HCCB 10218	GCF_001278075.1_ASM127807v1
<i>Streptomyces clavuligerus</i> ATCC 27064	GCF_005519465.1_ASM551946v1
<i>Streptomyces clavuligerus</i> F1D-5	GCF_003454755.1_ASM345475v1
<i>Streptomyces clavuligerus</i> F613-1	GCF_001693675.1_ASM169367v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. GSSD-12	GCF_003344965.1_ASM334496v1
<i>Streptomyces niveus</i> SCSIO 3406	GCF_002009175.1_ASM200917v1
<i>Streptomyces atratus</i> SCSIO ZH16	GCF_003330865.1_ASM333086v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. SM18	GCF_002910775.2_ASM291077v2
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. Sv. ACTE SirexAA-E	GCF_000177195.2_ASM17719v2
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. PAMC26508	GCF_000364805.1_ASM36480v1
<i>Streptomyces pratensis</i> ATCC 33331	GCF_000176115.2_ASM17611v2
<i>Streptomyces fulvissimus</i> DSM 40593	GCF_000385945.1_ASM38594v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. S8	GCF_002094995.1_ASM209499v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. CFMR 7	GCF_001278095.1_ASM127809v1
<i>Streptomyces bacillaris</i> ATCC 15855	GCF_003268675.1_ASM326867v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. DUT11	GCF_002848525.1_ASM284852v1
<i>Streptomyces violaceoruber</i> S21	GCF_002082175.1_ASM208217v1
<i>Streptomyces griseus</i> NBRC 13350	GCF_000010605.1_ASM1060v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. S063	GCF_002832675.1_ASM283267v1
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. Tue6075	GCF_001931635.1_ASM193163v1
<i>Streptomyces globisporus</i> C-1027	GCF_000261345.2_ASM26134v2
<i>Streptomyces globisporus</i> TFH56	GCF_003147545.1_ASM314754v1

Supplementary Table S2. Largest operons found in *S. clavuligerus* genome by Rockhopper.

Replicon	Start	Stop	Strand	Number of Genes	Genes	Function
Chromosome	2507976	251480 1	-	15	CRV15_RS10220, rplE, rplX, rplN, rpsQ, rpmC, rplP, rpsC, rplV, rpsS, rplB, rplW, rplD, rplC, rpsJ	Ribosomal Proteins
Chromosome	650154	664570	-	14	CRV15_RS02615, CRV15_RS02620, CRV15_RS02625, CRV15_RS02630, CRV15_RS02635, CRV15_RS02640, CRV15_RS02645, CRV15_RS02650, CRV15_RS02655, CRV15_RS02660, CRV15_RS02665, CRV15_RS02670, CRV15_RS02675, CRV15_RS35805	Unknown
Chromosome	2584193	2600408	-	14	nuoN, CRV15_RS10615, nuoL, nuoK, CRV15_RS10630, nuoI, nuoH, CRV15_RS10645, nuoF, nuoE, CRV15_RS10660, CRV15_RS10665, CRV15_RS10670, CRV15_RS10675	NADH-quinone oxidoreductase
Chromosome	6640616	6653838	-	13	CRV15_RS27890, CRV15_RS27895, CRV15_RS27900, CRV15_RS27905, CRV15_RS27910, CRV15_RS27915, CRV15_RS27920, CRV15_RS27925, CRV15_RS27930, CRV15_RS27935, CRV15_RS27940,	Unknown

					CRV15_RS27945, CRV15_RS27950	
Chromosome	67910	79603	-	11	rfbC, CRV15_RS00305, CRV15_RS00310, CRV15_RS00315, CRV15_RS00320, CRV15_RS00325, CRV15_RS00330, CRV15_RS00335, CRV15_RS00340, CRV15_RS00345, CRV15_RS00350	10-epi-HSAF
Chromosome	3812903	3821924	+	11	CRV15_RS15945, CRV15_RS15950, CRV15_RS15955, CRV15_RS15960, CRV15_RS35950, CRV15_RS15965, CRV15_RS15970, CRV15_RS15975, CRV15_RS15980, CRV15_RS15985, CRV15_RS15990	Unknown
Chromosome	1794835	1803517	+	10	CRV15_RS07120, CRV15_RS07125, CRV15_RS07130, galE, CRV15_RS07140, CRV15_RS07145, CRV15_RS07150, CRV15_RS07155, CRV15_RS07160, CRV15_RS07165	Tunicamycin B1 biosynthetic gene cluster
Chromosome	2548305	2558682	-	10	CRV15_RS10460, CRV15_RS10465, CRV15_RS10470, nuoK, CRV15_RS10480, CRV15_RS10485, CRV15_RS10490, CRV15_RS10495,	NADH-quinone oxidoreductase

					CRV15_RS10500, CRV15_RS10505	
Plasmid	286029	305141	-	12	CRV15_RS29555, CRV15_RS29560, CRV15_RS29565, CRV15_RS29570, sbnB, sbnA, CRV15_RS29585, CRV15_RS29590, CRV15_RS29595, CRV15_RS29600, CRV15_RS29605, CRV15_RS29610	(-)- δ -cadinene biosynthetic gene cluster
Plasmid	1033163	1044045	+	11	CRV15_RS32770, pgl, CRV15_RS32780, CRV15_RS32785, CRV15_RS32790, CRV15_RS32795, CRV15_RS32800, CRV15_RS32805, CRV15_RS32810, CRV15_RS32815, CRV15_RS32820	Low similarity to depsibosamycin B biosynthetic gene cluster
Plasmid	426676	433468	+	8	CRV15_RS30215, CRV15_RS30220, CRV15_RS30225, CRV15_RS30230, CRV15_RS30235, CRV15_RS30240, CRV15_RS30245, CRV15_RS30250	Unknown

Supplementary Table S3. Antismash Predictions for *S. clavuligerus*

Region	Type	From	To	Most similar known cluster		Similarity
Region 1.1	NI-siderophore	2,794	34,362	peucechelin	NRP	25%
Region 1.2	NRPS-like,other,NRPS,T1PKS,terpene	77,561	175,333	SGR PTMs/SGR PTM Compound b/SGR PTM Compound c/SGR PTM Compound d	NRP+Polyketide	83%
Region 1.3	T3PKS,ranthipeptide	278,060	319,115	naringenin	Polyketide:Type III polyketide	100%
Region 1.4	NRPS,NRPS-like	459,596	508,869	nucleocidin	Other	47%
Region 1.5	NRPS	527,573	570,863	holomycin	NRP	100%
Region 1.6	terpene	578,227	605,009	hopene	Terpene	69%
Region 1.7	NRPS	684,211	727,552			
Region 1.8	redox-cofactor	750,603	772,973	lankacidin C	NRP+Polyketide	20%
Region 1.9	lanthipeptide-class-iii,T2PKS	926,046	1,019,570	spore pigment	Polyketide	83%
Region 1.10	RiPP-like	1,041,263	1,052,636			
Region 1.11	NRPS	1,163,792	1,242,550	A-201A	Other	15%
Region 1.12	NI-siderophore	1,282,132	1,312,183	kinamycin	Polyketide	19%
Region 1.13	T1PKS,NRPS	1,543,626	1,598,790	asukamycin	Polyketide:Type II polyketide	3%
Region 1.14	lanthipeptide-class-i	1,653,875	1,679,161			
Region 1.15	nucleoside	1,782,683	1,803,654	tunicamycin B1	Other:Nucleoside	85%
Region 1.16	NRPS,bactam	1,861,345	1,912,633	cephamycin C	NRP:Beta-lactam	84%
Region 1.17	melanin	2,231,583	2,242,017	melanin	Other	100%

Region 1.18	blactam	3,301,354	3,322,328	alanylclavam/2-hydroxymethylclavam/2-formyloxymethylclavam/clavam-2-carboxylate	Other:Non-NRP beta-lactam	75%
Region 1.19	aminopolycarboxylic-acid	3,561,811	3,575,400	EDHA	Other	77%
Region 1.20	lanthipeptide-class-i	3,834,469	3,859,566			
Region 1.21	butyrolactone	4,011,689	4,022,657	lactonamycin	Polyketide	3%
Region 1.22	NRPS	4,028,923	4,076,251	clipibicyclene/azabicyclene B/azabicyclene C/azabicyclene D	NRP+Polyketide	11%
Region 1.23	NI-siderophore	4,422,537	4,452,357	desferrioxamin B	Other	100%
Region 1.24	ectoine	5,423,823	5,434,248	ectoine	Other	100%
Region 1.25	PKS-like,LAP,butyrolactone, T1PKS	6,066,295	6,153,436	4-hexadecanoyl-3-hydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)-2H-furan-5-one	Polyketide	63%
Region 1.26	terpene	6,504,864	6,527,038	geosmin	Terpene	100%
Region 1.27	T1PKS	6,653,964	6,748,591	JBIR-100	Polyketide:Modular type I polyketide	72%
Region 2.1	terpene	76,246	97,502	(+)-T-muurolol	Terpene	80%
Region 2.2	NRPS,NRPS-like,terpene	255,612	334,765	(-)- δ -cadinene	Terpene	100%
Region 2.3	lassopeptide	390,856	413,322			
Region 2.4	terpene	471,472	492,503	cyslabdan	Terpene	18%

Region 2.5	indole,NRPS-like,terpene	538,336	599,445	abyssomicin M/abyssomicin N/abyssomicin O/abyssomicin P/abyssomicin Q/abyssomicin R/abyssomicin S/abyssomicin T/abyssomicin U/abyssomicin V/abyssomicin W/abyssomicin X	Polyketide	9%
Region 2.6	terpene,lanthipeptide-class-iv	643,291	670,905	venezuelin	RiPP:Lanthipeptide	100%
Region 2.7	terpene	800,510	821,475			
Region 2.8	butyrolactone	861,601	872,533			
Region 2.9	amglyccycl,terpene,T1PKS,NRPS	1,026,084	1,098,543	depsibosamycin B/depsibosamycin C/depsibosamycin D	NRP	23%
Region 2.10	blactam	1,142,847	1,164,448	alanylclavam/2-hydroxymethylclavam/2-formyloxymethylclavam/clavam-2-carboxylate/clavulanic acid	Other:Non-NRP beta-lactam	100%
Region 2.11	indole	1,199,815	1,223,432	staurosporine	Alkaloid	82%
Region 2.12	RiPP-like	1,229,724	1,241,718			
Region 2.13	terpene	1,286,162	1,318,471	primycin	Polyketide	5%
Region 2.14	melanin,T1PKS	1,334,215	1,388,170	neocarzinostatin	Polyketide:Iterative type I polyketide+Polyketide:Enediyne type I polyketide	17%

Region 2.15	T1PKS,NRPS-like,phosphoglycolipid,NRPS,ectoine	1,392,244	1,557,780	maduropeptin	Polyketide:Iterative type I polyketide+Polyketide:Enediyne type I polyketide	37%
Region 2.16	terpene,NRPS	1,594,503	1,656,265	rapamycin	NRP+Polyketide	7%
Region 2.17	NRPS-like	1,668,918	1,712,991	minimycin	NRP+Saccharide	40%